

Synthesis and Fungi Toxicity of some Halogeno-Poly-Nitro Aryl Esters of *o*-Methyl and *o*-Ethyl-Xanthic Acids

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Twenty halogenonitrophenyl ester of *O*-methyl- and *O*-ethyl-Xanthic acids have been prepared by the condensation of halogenonitrobenzenes and Potassium *O*-methyl- and *O*-ethyl Xanthates. They have been characterised and tested for their antifungal activity against *Alternaria Tenis*, *Helminthosporium sativum*, *Aspergillus Niger* and *Colleotrichem gleosporide* by spore germination method. A relation between fungitoxicity and structure has also been established.

A LARGE number of salts of *o*-alkyl derivatives of thionthiol known as xanthate have been reported in recent years to possess fungicidal activity against *Conidia* of *M. Fructicola*^{1,2}. The potassium xanthate upto C₈ were tested for toxicity in mice and *Tubifex-tubifex* worms³. They have also been used in the concentration of ores⁴ by the floatation process. Xanthates with choline are used as drugs and cosmetics⁵. A perusal of literature on the xanthates revealed that mostly they have been used as metallic salts with very little emphasis on the esters. The esters of xanthic acid show the property of chemiluminescence in air⁶. The benzyl ester of butyl xanthate is used as insecticide for red spider⁷. As halogens and nitro groups are known to modify the biological activity of organic molecules, we now report the synthesis of halogenonitroaryl esters of *o*-methyl and *o*-ethyl xanthates.

The esters⁸ (III) have been obtained by the condensation of halogenonitrobenzene (I) with the potassium salt of *O*-substituted xanthic acid⁹ (II) in ethanolic solution at 20°–50°. Thus, 1-chloro-2,4-dinitro-, 1-chloro-2,6-dinitro-, 1-chloro-2,4,6-trinitro-, 1,3-dichloro-4,6-dinitro-, 1,4-dichloro-2,6-dinitro-, 1-chloro-3-methyl-4,6-dinitro-, 1-chloro-4-methyl-2,6-dinitro-, 1,2,3-trichloro-4,6-dinitro-, 1,2-dichloro-3-methyl-4,6-dinitro- and 1,3-dichloro-2-methyl-4,6-dinitrobenzenes on condensation with potassium salt of *O*-methyl and *O*-ethyl xanthates give 2,4-dinitro-,

2,6-dinitro-, 2,4,6-trinitro-, 3-chloro-4,6-dinitro-, 4-chloro-2,6-dinitro-, 4-methyl-2,6-dinitro-, 3-methyl-2,4,6-trinitro-, 2,3-dichloro-4,6-dinitro-, 2-chloro-3-methyl-4,6-dinitro-, 3-chloro-2-methyl-4,6-dinitrophenyl esters of *O*-methyl (Table 1) and *O*-ethyl (Table 2) xanthic acids respectively. The I.R. data of these compounds have also been recorded and is in complete agreement with their structure.

These compounds were tested for their antifungal activity against *Alternaria tenis*, *Helminthosporium sativum*, *Aspergillus niger* and *Colleotrichem gleosporide* by spore germination method¹⁰ (Tables 1 and 2). The dosages in $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ required for the inhibition of the 50% growth of the fungi have been recorded.

Experimental

Potassium salt of O-substituted xanthate: A solution of alcohol (10 ml.), potassium hydroxide (0.1 mol.) and ether was boiled under reflux till all the potassium hydroxide had reacted. The solution was cooled to 0°–5° and carbondisulphide (0.1 M) added to it drop by drop during a period of half an hour, maintaining the temperature between 10°–15° and stirring till the precipitate of the potassium *O*-substituted xanthic acid was obtained. It was crystallised out of alcohol.

Halogenonitrophenyl esters of O-substituted xanthic acid: A solution of halogenonitrobenzene (0.01 M) in ethanol was added dropwise to a cooled solution of potassium alkyl xanthate (0.01 M) with constant shaking and maintaining the temperature between 20°–50°. Stirring was continued for another half an hour. The product that separated out was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from alcohol.

The esters are insoluble in water and easily soluble in acetone. Their melting points, yield and analytical data have been recorded in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1—HALOGENONITROPHENYL ESTERS OF O-METHYL XANTHIC ACID

$$\text{CH}_3\text{-O-C-S-R}$$

$$\parallel$$

$$\text{S}$$

S.No.	R	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. Formula	% Sulphur		Dosages required for the inhibition of 50% of growth in $\mu\text{gms}/\text{cm}^2$			
					Found	Required	AN	AT	HS	CG
1.	2,4-DNP	192	90	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{N}_2\text{O}_6\text{S}_2$	23.36	23.35	100	110	100	102
2.	2,6-DNP	218	75	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{N}_2\text{O}_5\text{S}_2$	23.49	23.35	80	93	90	78
3.	2,4,6-TNP	139	80	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_5\text{N}_3\text{O}_7\text{S}_2$	19.86	20.06	75	80	76	75
4.	3-Chloro-4,6-DNP	101	85	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_5\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_6\text{S}_2$	20.54	20.78	180	250	182	190
5.	4-Chloro-2,6-DNP	125	91	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_5\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_6\text{S}_2$	20.62	20.78	90	80	85	92
6.	3-Methyl-4,6-DNP	85	95	$\text{C}_9\text{H}_9\text{N}_2\text{O}_6\text{S}_2$	22.39	22.22	201	200	250	180
7.	4-Methyl-2,6-DNP	102	70	$\text{C}_9\text{H}_9\text{N}_2\text{O}_6\text{S}_2$	22.36	22.22	105	105	104	110
8.	2,3-Dichloro-4,6-DNP	80	88	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_4\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_6\text{S}_2$	18.87	18.65	105	95	100	100
9.	2-Chloro-3-methyl-4,6-DNP	119	90	$\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_6\text{S}_2$	19.97	19.87	109	106	104	91
10.	3-Chloro-2-methyl-4,6-DNP	105	70	$\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_6\text{S}_2$	19.82	19.87	150	160	170	181

TABLE 2—HALOGENONITROPHENYL ESTERS OF O-ETHYL XANTHIC ACID

$$\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{-O-C-S-R}$$

$$\parallel$$

$$\text{S}$$

S.No.	R	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. Formula	% Sulphur		Dosages required for the inhibition of 50% of growth in $\mu\text{gms}/\text{cm}^2$			
					Found	Required	AN	AT	HS	CG
1.	2,4-DNP	185	93	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{N}_2\text{O}_6\text{S}_2$	22.35	22.22	120	102	100	102
2.	2,6-DNP	135	75	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{N}_2\text{O}_6\text{S}_2$	22.17	22.22	105	100	78	80
3.	2,4,6-TNP	100	90	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_3\text{O}_7\text{S}_2$	19.37	19.21	80	85	75	75
4.	3-Chloro-4,6-DNP	122	95	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_6\text{S}_2$	19.59	19.87	190	250	185	195
5.	4-Chloro-2,6-DNP	131	89	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_6\text{S}_2$	19.67	19.87	102	100	75	80
6.	3-Methyl-4,6-DNP	110	70	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_2\text{O}_6\text{S}_2$	21.23	21.19	180	150	180	130
7.	4-Methyl-2,6-DNP	101	85	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_2\text{O}_6\text{S}_2$	21.09	21.19	110	108	120	100
8.	2,3-Dichloro-4,6-DNP	62	80	$\text{C}_9\text{H}_8\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_6\text{S}_2$	17.71	17.92	108	102	100	105
9.	2-Chloro-3-methyl-4,6-DNP	121	90	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_9\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_6\text{S}_2$	19.19	19.04	150	135	130	120
10.	3-Chloro-2-methyl-4,6-DNP	140	80	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_9\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_6\text{S}_2$	19.15	19.04	162	175	195	180

DNP & TNP refers to dinitro and trinitrophenyl respectively. All melting points are uncorrected. Satisfactory C, H analysis have been obtained for all these compounds.

AN, AT, HS and CG refers to *Aspergillus niger*, *Alternaria tenuis*, *Helminthosporium sativum* and *Colleotrichum gloeosporide* respectively.

Results and Discussion

The fungitoxicity of the esters of O-substituted xanthic acids depends on both the ester moiety and the dithiocarbonate moiety. In the ester moiety the fungitoxicity of nitroaryl esters sharply increases with the number of nitro groups at ortho and para positions to the ester linkage. Similarly a halogen atom increases fungitoxicity when placed at the ortho or para position to the ester linkage. However, a halogen atom at the meta position seems to decrease it. The effect of methyl group on the fungitoxicity is rather abnormal. It decreases fungitoxicity when present at the ortho and meta positions at the ester

linkage and increases it when present at the para position.

In the dithiocarbonate moiety the presence of the lower alkyl group generally increases the fungitoxicity. O-Methyl is more fungitoxic than O-ethylxanthates.

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